

A Critical Study of the Multifarious Uses of Music and Song in Femi Osofisan's Midnight Hotel

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Abstract

This paper is focused on critically evaluating the potential and power of music and song in the theatre craft. The paper critically examines the various roles music and song play in Osofisan's Midnight Hotel play. Music and song in this play have been, summoned by Osofisan in the quest for experimentation and a radical ideological presentation of the socio-political ills in the post-colonial Nigeria. In this play, Osofisan subverts the Nigerian political and historical background to create a comic operatic satire. In this experimental work, music and song play a wide variety of functions: from being a major character with a strong voice to creating a sensitive aesthetic entertaining and evocative mien in the work. Through these resources, Osofisan is able to criticize the society and elicit responses from his audience while mobilizing them to participate in the play.

Key words: *music, song, multifarious, Africa, festival, drama.*

Introduction

The African Primitive Traditional Theatre has become the bedrock of modern theatre in the Africa Continent. A robust and rich theatrical practice and tradition exists and has always existed in Africa. What has flourished today as modern Nigerian theatre is a consequence and an offshoot of traditional theatre.

Before the arrival of the colonial masters to Africa, the continent was teeming with performance activities in form of ceremonies, festivals, religious rites, storytelling and various kinds of celebrations, all interwoven into the daily life of the various African cultures (Oscar Brockett 1968). The African is a very expressive and religious person, who maintains a devotional life style. He believes

in the interference of the spiritual in the daily affairs of man. This becomes a driving impulse that gives impetus to celebrations of many kinds and a ritualistic lifestyle to appease the gods of the land (Aihevba and Atere, 2017). A public performance was the usual medium of expression and communication in indigenous African cultures. One kind or another of performance went on throughout the year's circle.

Ruth Finnegan (1976) argues that the traditional performances in African festivals approximated to drama. According to her, the masquerade (dances of masks figure of various kinds) which flourish throughout Africa all includes elements of drama often referred to as 'play'. She opines that there is usually some kind of enactment

by the masked figures with great emphasis on costume, music, dance with little or no linguistic content and sometimes a rudimentary plot. Even though most African culture had no written modes in the precolonial times, much of what Africans considered to be of historical importance was embodied and preserved in their performances.

The development of drama and theatre in Nigeria has leveraged greatly on the fundamental resources of traditional theatre and the western culture via colonial. In Nigeria, colonialism has created a complex and dynamic breed of theatre in Africa. First, contemporary writers and performers have at their disposal three languages to choose from: the language of the colonial imperialists, Pidgin English and one of the indigenous languages. Drawing from the rich cultural indigenous forms of festivals, ceremonies, rituals and storytelling, contemporary theater in Nigeria, is embellished richly with, other languages especially those of drumming, dancing and singing, which often communicate in addition to visual imagery, symbolism, gestures and so on. Quite often, the Nigerian theatre is used as an instrument of social change and development. It goes beyond theatre for entertainment. For most part it is satirical, always attacking structures and addressing contemporary concerns since the colonial days till date. Femi Osofisan, a leading Nigerian dramatist is a champion in this regard.

Osofisan and Socialist Drama in Nigeria

Femi Osofisan believes in the socialist cause. As far as he is concerned, man's problems originated from man and not from any metaphysical or spiritual realm. Therefore, only man can solve his own problems. To Osofisan and his contemporaries, art is a relevant and a potent instrument of social mobilization. Drama must be functional in terms of arousing the consciousness of the masses in order to effect a change for a better society through collective action. To them, drama is a potent ideological tool for liberating the oppressed masses. The major ideology on which his crusade is based is the Marxist philosophy which he effectively propagates with Bertolt Brecht's epic theatre technique. Osofisan, like his compatriots, has also greatly embellished his art with other languages and resources which he has borrowed

from the traditional theatre archives. He relies on music, song and dance which often communicates shades of deeper meanings to his audience.

To ensure audience participation in his drama experience, and to communicate his complex ideology, Femi Osofisan uses songs, music and dance. We shall be looking in this work at how Osofisan has used music and song artistically, uniquely and experimentally to create meaning and aesthetics in his *The Midnight Hotel* play.

A Conspectus of Midnight Hotel

Midnight Hotel is a comic opera, a hilarious comedy which uses the theatrical devices of humour, music and song to satirize political corruption, religious immorality and economic mismanagement in the Nigerian society, especially during the Aihaji Shehu Shagari's second republic. It lashes out against the moral decadence, political corruption, the pretence and materialism of the so-called religious leaders and other ills. The society is portrayed as one engulfed in deep spiritual slumber where wrong is celebrated as right. The objective of Osofisan in this play is to, through the element of sarcasm, show us ourselves in a laughable and humorous way, for he believes that in spite of the hardship and struggle;

We must never allow laughter to die out on our lips... we must develop and nurture the courage to be free. We must never allow our bitterness to clutter up, and corrupt our imaginative spaces... we must laugh in order to be, and remain human. And we must remain human, in order to laugh (Osofisan 1986:5).

Midnight Hotel delineates through effective character portrayal, ills like political corruption, moral depravity and religious charlatanism that plague the Nigerian society and mentality. Awero, a female member of parliament like other members insists on having sex with Pastor Suru a would-be contractor in the name of 'sampling the goods'. Awero takes the hypocritical and fanatical Pastor Suru, a friend of her husband, who has a Swiss bank account to the Midnight Hotel to sample him. At the Hotel, which is a place of clandestine immorality

and a metaphor for corruption, they meet Alatise a family friend and head master who has come to lodge at the Hotel with his three daughters. Awero also runs into her husband Asibong who coincidentally has come to the hotel that night as a housing agent inspector. The unexpected presence of both Alatise, Asibong and the rude interruptions of the hotel attendants, prevents Awero from sampling Pastor Suru.

Jimoh, the senior hotel attendant is full of himself and a victim of foolish personal aggrandizement, who will do anything for a chieftaincy title. He seeks importance and significance from titles and praises thus showing his hollow nature. Alatise's three daughters resort to sexual immorality to survive, a reflection of the organized prostitution plaguing the Nigerian society today. Alatise, is robbed in the elections in which he contested as a candidate. With no wife and three children who have suddenly indulged in sexual immorality at the Midnight Hotel for survival, Alatise caves in and gives up, resigning to suicide instead of struggle and revolt against evil; demonstrating the lack of resilience and spiritual will to never give up. Alatise, however, survives by a stroke of luck. In the *Midnight Hotel*, Osofisan combines the Brechtian Epic theatre with Feydeau's theatre of illusion to create a unique style: the comic opera that is quintessentially Osofisan's.

Brechtian Epic Theatre

One of the greatest influence on Femi Osofisan as a playwright is the Brechtian Epic Theatre. It must be noted that Osofisan and Brecht have a similarity of purpose as regards the purpose and impact of the theatre on the society. They both perceive the theatre as an instrument of instruction and social change set up to demolish the structures of oppression and exploitation erected by the bourgeois exploiters. Adesumbo (1995) believes that:

Femi Osofisan's policy of using drama as an instrument of change is similar to Brecht's influence on him in playwriting because even he, Osofisan, personally identifies

himself with the Brechtian school of thought and one of the dominant techniques of Osofisan's drama is Brecht's epic form (10).

The Epic Theatre as a style developed out of the expressionist movement. Expressionism was an artistic effort to express thoughts and emotions by showing the inner life of the characters on stage, rather than what the characters represents in the material world. Although Erwin Piscator pioneered the Epic Theatre, Brecht became its major theoretician and dramatist. Brecht saw his style as "epic" since it embraced a broad approach and a mixture of narrative and dramatic techniques.

The major focus of the Epic Theatre is distancing the audience from stage dramatic actions. Before its existence, the audience has been a passive one that sees the actions on stage as entertainment. Brecht expected the spectator of a stage performance to be actively involved in the action on stage. Brecht expected the spectator to be aroused by the actions, so that he can critically assess the actions and take immediate decisions. Brecht hoped that the spectator would relate what he sees on stage to the socio-economic conditions of the real world and to apply this new theatrical experience to the outside world. The emotional conditions of the characters on stage, rather than evoke pity and fear in the spectator, ought to evoke criticism and argument.

To achieve this objective, Brecht employed the technique of alienation, which tends to make the actions onstage strange, unusual to the spectator so as to arouse questions about them. To create this situation and aid the spectator in his questioning, Brecht created theatrical techniques such as lighting instruments, music, scene changes, design techniques, historicification etc. to deter the audience from empathizing with the actions on stage.

Feydean Theatre of Illusion

Georges Feydeau (1862 – 1921) French dramatist known for his farces with elaborate plots, often dealing with cases of marital infidelity or mistaken identity, Feydeau's matchless perception of the frailty of end-of-the-century

respectability and in superb economy in writing reveal his skill as not simply a light entertainer but an accomplished writer of satire. Faydean's plays do not lend themselves well to reading but rely on the dynamics of the visual dramatic mechanism committing of impossible coincidences, complicated stage direction and failures of communication.

His dramaturgy was to bring to perfection 'the farce' a genre initiated by 19th Century French Playwright Eugene Labiche. His honour relied on complex and highly efficient plots, usually improbable and continued, in which the slightest threat to middle class order can give way to an unstoppable series of mishaps, leading to disastrous conclusions. He regarded his comedies as so called reverse tragedies, but they were generally regarded as theatre of illusion. His ferocious farces dealt with matrimonial difficulties. (See "Georges Feydean" Microsoft Student 2008 (DVD). Redmond, WA: Microsoft Corporation, 2007).

What is Music?

The New Lexicon Webster's Dictionary of the English Language defines music as "the art of giving structural form and rhythmic pattern to combinations of sounds produced instrumentally or vocally". Abolagba et al (2003:162) agrees with the general definition that defines music as "the combination of sounds that is pleasing to the ears". He informs us that sound is the main source of music. Butler David (2008:1) sees music as: "The artful arrangement of sounds across time". Even though this definition is very broad, it corroborates what has already been established above. It is interesting to note that music is virtually a part of every culture on earth. Tribes and tongues and nations and peoples all participate in this art. So, it is expected that the definition, style and structure of the art must vary from ethnicity to ethnicity. In spite of these variations one thing is clear, most musical experiences involve producing or listening to physical characteristics of sound such as pitch and timbre-quality comparable to texture or color in sight (Butler 2008).

Music is one of the most potent, most common and most expressive means of communication. The language of

music is ethnic and yet universal. Butler has this to say about the language of music:

Like language, another arrangement of sounds, music is a uniquely human form of communication with well developed rules of construction much like grammar. Some language experts would say that you can listen to someone speaking a language you do not understand and still know whether (he speaker is excited or tired, angry or delighted. You would be making interpretation based upon the speech patterns: loud or soft, high pitched or low pitched, rapid and bitten off or slow and smooth. Corresponding to these elements of speech are musical variables such as dynamics (force and volume), register (range of music or voice), mode (arrangement of a set of tones), and articulation (such as staccato, meaning abrupt and crisp; or legato, smooth and even) (1)

Even though it is not clear and there is no general agreement as to what music communicates and how it communicates, there is a general consensus about the power and potency of music to arouse feelings, remold behavior and communicate in an especial way. Most ancient Greek philosophers including Plato believe that listening to certain kinds of music was beneficial to the development of a young person's character. For centuries Chinese music was influenced by the philosophy of Confucius: that music was not to entertain but to purify one's thoughts. Also, in Africa, folk music is known to contain strong ethical and moral values which are transferred to the next generation during rendition.

Music is also a great way of documenting a people's tradition, beliefs, religion, social interaction, environment, history, hopes, aspirations, Feelings emotions and their passionate drives. Music and song are the most physical insignia that distinguish the culture of one group from another. It is a timeless art that embodies a totality of their way of life. In Africa the lack of musical notation system and other systems of

documentation has made it impossible to adequately capture the great musical heritage of Africa in ancient times, the relics that have survived to today have been passed down through the generations orally (by singing) and aurally (by listening).

Following this definition, we find out that Bini music, for example, rely primarily on drums (ema), metal gongs (egogo), and gourd rattles (ukuse) to create a distinctive, traditional musical style. Many cultures are still defined by their distinct music today.

What Is Song?

The New Lexicon Webster's Dictionary of the English Language conceives of song as "a short composition in which words and music together form a unity". In the same vein, the Microsoft Encarta dictionary views song as "a usually relatively short musical composition consisting of words set to music and the music itself". The two definitions have striking similarities in that songs are a combination of words and rhythm or lyric and music. The latter definition is rather remarkable because it describes song as "the music itself". Song can, therefore, be correctly referred to as music.

Song is the art of singing. It is a composition for the voice. Songs employ music, lyric and the voice to express meaning. Vinton John (2007:1) describes song as a lyric or narrative text set to music. To him, music only reproduces the mood of the song and gives heightened emotional expression to the song's text, which is often a poem. Songs are intimately united with poetry in the sense that songs represent a rhythmic expression of man's deep passionate and intense emotional feelings through a unique reordering of language and sound devices.

In singing, the lungs play the role of an air reservoir and bellows, forcing air between the vocal cords and causing them to vibrate. The resultant sound is amplified as it resonates in the cavities of the chest, neck and head and is articulated by the singer's lips, teeth, tongue and palate (resonating as consonants and vowels): Encarta dictionary (2007). Variation in singing styles can help to determine mood, occasion, culture and gender. Through observable fillers like tone, physical tension, acoustic intensity, pitch ranges, melodic ornamentation, the use or

avoidance of rasps, yelps, growls and other colourful voice modification, one can observe a distinction in cultural choices. The Fulani cultural singing pattern for example is characterized by high pitch ranges and solo singing compared to the Edos which are comparatively low pitched and choral singing. Song texts can help to create or alter emotional climate by the meaning it can evoke. A mourning song is therefore characteristically distinct from a celebration song, because of the meanings of the set of words and the pitch/tempo of the songs. Also, in Africa, high penetrating for women and low voices for men are favoured.

A very outstanding quality of songs is that they can possess melodies, lyrics and accompaniments that are typical of certain cultures; these are referred to as folk songs. Folk songs or folk music are songs typical of a musically unsophisticated culture that is originated by and is part of the tradition of a people. In describing the features of folk music Nett Bruno (2008) opines that:

it consists of song or pieces taught through performances rather than notation (written musical notes,) and learned by hearing. The original composers of folk music are anonymous or forgotten. A folk song does not have a standardized form. Instead, its words as well as its music exist in more than and sometimes a great many variants or in slightly different versions... folk music is generally simpler and more compact in style than classical or art music (1).

In Africa, and indeed Nigeria, there is a rich tradition of folk music that existed long ago and still flourishes today. Folk songs play a great role in African societies. It is an integral part of the lives, hopes, dreams, aspirations, ritual, worship and social life of the people. In this musical resource is opulently documented the history, and the identity of the Nigerian people. It articulates their beliefs, their fears and the totality of their existence. As a result of the fact that the African is deeply religious, special folk songs are used to worship ancestral gods and invoke/sustain their presence. Folk music is the cardinal agency through which the bond between mortals and the gods is reaffirmed and renewed.

In one African festival, folk music could play many functions including signal and announcement, processions, evocative functions, the panegyric and historical function, the satirical and the entertainment function, the prayer and supplication function and so on. Agreeing with the multifarious functions of folk music in Africa (Ebighgbo 2005) asserts that:

The various stages of the cycle of an individual and the life cycle of society are all marked with music. For the life cycle of an individual: birth, childhood, manhood and death are marked with music. For the life cycle of the society: the change of seasons the beginning and end of agricultural activities, war and peace, joy and sorrow, etc, are all mark with music (128).

Subsequently, we have ritual songs, war songs, burial songs, work song, panegyrics, celebration songs, and so on. From the foregoing, folk music ensures the continuity and stability of cultures. It allows emotional expression, gives aesthetic pleasure, help to enforce conformity to social order and religious institutions - folk songs and music is one of the structures that hold the fabrics of society together.

The Uses of Music and Song in *Midnight Hotel*

Being a musical satire, it is not surprising that music was elaborately used in *Midnight Hotel*. The framework of the play is built on music and song. The play opens and closes with music. In all, nine lengthy songs were performed, and all the ten characters participated in the music that was opulently provided by the Petronaira Band, a play group resident at the hotel. The audience is also expected to be active participants in the music and dance going on up stage. Music played a variety of functions in this play: it was used as commentary and commentator; used to stimulate and sustain audience interest and participation; used to enforce the Brechtian Alienation effect; used as interludes; and of course, used to create a rich aesthetic and evocative atmosphere.

In this play, music was more than a mere utensil of entertainment but rather an imposing character and

audience. Music had an intense voice, louder than that of the other characters, commenting, observing and instigating. The theme of immorality, exploitation, political corruption, economic mismanagement and revolution were clearly expressed in the songs. The spiritual slumber, political aridity, social banality and the moral decadence of Nigeria which are represented by the *Midnight Hotel* are promptly unveiled in the “song master’s welcome song” which is the signature tune of the petronaira Band as they welcome the customers:

Well, this place was built a house of sin in the year nineteen hundred and fourteen with just three rooms at the beginning.

Then came independence, and shortly after our customers and our staff began to slaughter one another with such abandon, and such cheerful license, that soon, our management group was chased out by the new messiah in khaki The commandos of rice, and oil and pepper soup who kindly led us form chaos to anarchy.

So who cares any more how many rooms there are? Just join us for our crimes!

Our specialty is in those secret games which men indulge in, and nations sometimes: we’ve got them all just place your order.

For we’ll always be here, always open even when war engulfs the nation: The war of scarcity, or that of inflation, or the one which you call elections coming upon us now like a huge conflagration (10).

In this signature tune of welcome, dates and numbers are deliberately coded – the year 1914 refers to the historic amalgamation of the Northern and southern protectorates and Lagos colony to form the state now known as Nigeria with three regions under Lord Lugard as the governor general. The song also exposes and condemns all forms of corruption, political treachery, immorality, perversion and other vices that trailed independence. These led to the military take over which made matters even worse and dragged the country into more mess.

All the songs in the play raise probing question, satirizes the abysmal degeneracy of the nation and make

philosophical comments on the state of things. “The song of the Lagos woman” for example comments on the corruption that has eaten deep into all the fabrics of the society engendering immorality, greed and the amassment of wealth all to spend on lust, vanity, extravagance and frivolities:

She goes to
Europe frequently
And when she comes down from the
skies
The men of customs prudently
They turn away their probing eyes.

But she’ll never tell oh no,
That the price she paid you know
For this her thriving trade
Was a little escapade at the Midnight
Hotel
For that is where the oil boom goes
She goes to social occasions
Her arms and feet all draped in gold
Her skin of strange pigmentations
She has her lovers manifold.

But she’ll never tell oh no
That the price was paid you know
For this superb parade
In a little escapade
At the Midnight Hotel
For that is where the oil boom goes (14)

The theme of political corruption and immorality is further amplified in the song “song in Praise of sampling the goods”:

The world’s a market, they say
And so is parliament so don’t bring us your
lament Unless you’re willing to pay

chorus:

But please, take off your clothes
And do not waste my time.
I want to sample your type
We made our own investment
When we came to campaign
So there’s no need to bargain
About our reimbursement

Chorus...

You cannot like government
If it not efficient;

How shall we give example
If we refuse to sample?

Chorus...(24)

In this song, Osofisan reduces the status, mentality and activities of our politicians to mere market women in the market place, whose major objective is to make profit after investing. This song drives home aptly the theme of spiritual aridity in our politicians.

The songs also strengthen, enhance and amplify the actions on stage. They react to the events and characters on stage as the playwright would like his audience to respond. They express opinions on the events of the play. The characters raise the ideas, and the songs develop and mature them. For example:

Alatise: ... Yes madam! It’s as bad as that! I even lost my deposit, yes as the song master will bear witness:

For that day you recall
We all went to the polls
As to a gambling house
And sonic had brought their words
The spell of rich rewards
And some had brought their stress
And some their bitterness
So many brought their greed
But those who lost deposit
Were those who brought their dreams
Who only brought their dreams!(47)

The “song of the Fairy mother” for example amplifies the ills that plague the Nigeria society like election fraud, legislative maneuvers, mismanagement and ineptitude

So said what’s – her name
And these lanes they won the vote, and
Ding – a – ling – o
They sit in parliament
Ding – a – ling – o (all our wealth these
fairies)
Impound
Ding – a ling – o
They stack all our funds
In foreign account
They eat in our name and
Ding – a ling – o
They drink in our name and

Ding – a – ling – o

While we shrink, these faries
Are round
Ding – a – ling – o
Ding – a – ling – o (68)

In the end, Osofian prescribed in a song the Marxist way of redemption from this bleak and dark state in which the nation is now wallowing in a song entitled “The Song of a faraway land”:

Once it was in a faraway land
in a once-familiar state
A once-familiar lime
The people had no peace
The people had no rest
For their leaders were always at war
Their leaders were always at war
All these leaders knew was to wreck the
land
And to such killing and looting
And dance around and give no ear,
While the people groaned everywhere

Spoken by song master;
We’ll chase away these exploiters, the
people said:
But look at who they put in their place!

Chorus:

Oh the winners are laughing now
And storing riches
In banks abroad:
But they forgot
They forgot the shah of Iran
That the Season can change at noon
And bring an evening of rain-oh
So let the winners go laughing on
Let the winners go laughing on
Thus it was in a faraway land
In a once-familiar state
A once familiar time
That thugs came to power.
And the people lost their rights
As the agents of terror seized the land
Bringing sorrow and pain on the land
Till the people woke up
And they got their guns
Against these liars and looters –
They learnt at last to pay the price:
Will you follow when it’s your turn?

Chorus...

No people can have peace
No people can have rest
Till the struggle for freedom is won
So the story just goes on and on
And the story goes on and on (86).

A critical look at this song brings to the fore, the major thrust and theme of the play. The narrative song gives us a history of political insincerity and exploitation of the masses. These heinous crimes and devilish activities of politicians once increased because the people went to sleep. However, when they woke up, they started a revolt against the liars and looters till peace returned. Through this song, Osofisan provides a blueprint and a plan of action to topple the exploiters. This song clearly projects Osofisan’s Marxist and radical view by prescribing that the only way to peace is revolution: steel, sweat and blood. The allusion to the shah of Iran in the song is a testimony of a strong historical dept, illustrative of the end of all oppressors as with the shah dynasty in Iran. The shah dynasty was the hereditary monarch of Iran in former times. Until the mass demonstrations against the shah (king) of Iran during the 1978 – 1979 Islamic revolution. The revolution culminated in the overthrow of Iran’s monarchy and the establishment of the Iranian parliament. The revolution was prompted by widespread corruption in the government of Iran. After a year of unrest, the wish of the people was enthroned. The shah agreed to the creation of the Majis (parliament). This allusion is a symbolic reminder of the power of collective resistance and the ultimate end of all oppressors and exploiters.

Through his lyrics, Osofisan protests and revolts against the social political and economic conditions of the Nigerian society: the squalor, corruption, injustice and misuse of state power. Through this song he takes a message to the proletariat and peasantry: that they must rise and seize their rights and denounce corrupt leadership. In this play, music and song are agents that encapsulate Osofisan’s political philosophy: the dislodgement of an oppressive and unjust political system (Awodiya 1995).

Another important role of music and dance in *Midnight Hotel* is the alienation effect. The deliberate inclusion of a life band (the Petronaira Band); an indefatigable song master as head of the orchestra and a visible character in the play; and a continuous interruption of the action on stage by music helps Osofisan achieve the Brechtian alienation technique. The intervention of the song master was deliberately included in such a way as to breach the naturalistic context of the play. The playwright even prescribed that “songs and orchestra should be deliberately isolated, as separate dramatic experiences from the normal flow of action”. This is meant to create the breaks in the play that ultimately divorces the audience from the action on stage thereby ensuring the distancing and logical detachment between the performance and the audience.

The characters call the song master to the stage at will to lead and direct the songs. For example:

Jimoh: ... wait (*He hurries across to the song master.*). Please, song master, you do have this song of the Lagos woman, don't you? (*song master answers in the affirmative*) Thank you. Let's sing it for this idiot!.. All these are experimental techniques to ensure the Brechtian alienation style.

Music and dance were also used creatively in this play to induce and arouse audience interest and participation. “The song master’s welcome song” which opens the play at the prologue wets the appetite of the audience, excites their expectation and arouses their interest and participation. Osofisan even prescribed in his stage direction that “As with all songs in the play, every encouragement should be given to the audience to participate – for instance, the songs could be projected onto the screen, or distributed along with the programme note”.

Music and songs are also used to fill intervals as the play progresses on the stage, ensuring continuity and sustaining interest. For example:

Jirnoh: ... poor fellow, he'll get used to it! (*He looks after Bicycle, shaking his head. Then he returns to his desk and, with the newspaper across his face, is soon asleep*

again. The orchestra fills in the interval with a verse of the “song of the Lagos woman).

Being a comic operatic satire, music and song are systematically engrafted to bring out the comic flavour of the play, inducing laughter and at the same time carrying a significant message. Music and song are used to create a lively atmosphere while expressing an acerbic message bitter to swallow but is chewed easily because of the hilarious mood of the play. As the girls sang and danced round the candle like three witches they enhance the comic situation of the play but ironically driving Asibong crazy. The balanced nature of the explosive energy of the songs and the sarcastic satire in the message makes the play a spectacle to behold.

Conclusion & Recommendation

Femi Osofisan’s dramaturgy is not a static mirror of society but rather an instrument that provokes the audience to action. He uses music, song and dance to question, query, interrogate and even prescribe a blueprint of action. Through the theatre, he is a social crusader devoted to using all the theatre resources at his disposal to cause positive change in society. This pragmatic approach of Osofisan should be adopted by playwrights and theatre practitioners. The moral decadence, political exploitation, and spiritual bareness and banality of our leaders must be observed not with indifference but rather the beauty and energy of arts must be summoned as a potent instrument of change in society. If we as artist do nothing and say nothing of our world, our precious Africa will be lost to death, decay and destruction.

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